

the largest conidial population (5.8×10^7 conidia/ml) at 30 DAI, after which numbers gradually declined. Three-fourths-filled bags showed an unchanged conidial population from 30 to 35 DAI (5

$\times 10^7$ conidia/ml), after which it started declining.

Polypropylene pipes (autoclavable) may be used to replace the hollow dry bamboo pieces. This technique is supe-

Integrated pest management—insects

Metarrhizium sp.: a new biocontrol agent for brown planthopper management in ricefields

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Agronomic practices and use of certain insecticides are the reported causes of increases in brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) populations. Continued use of insecticides was reported to be responsible for BPH epidemics in Sri Lanka, India, Philippines, and Indonesia.

We found that the fungus *Metarrhizium* sp. isolated from infected BPH in an untreated Sri Lankan ricefield caused very high mortality in BPH populations. Pathogenicity of the isolate AB301/1 was studied using BPH collected from wetland ricefields. Healthy BPH were reared on 2-mo-old rice plants of cultivar BG90-2 raised in clay pots (10 cm diam, 15 cm high), with 2.5 cm standing water. Plants were raised in a greenhouse at $30 \pm 4^\circ\text{C}$ and 60-75% RH. Twenty-five 18-d-old BPH in these pots were later sprayed with an atomizer containing 6.4×10^6 spores/ml of *Metarrhizium* sp. Treatments were replicated 10 times with distilled water

spray as a control. Pots were observed for dead insects every 24 h for 8 d.

The pathogen sporulated on the surface of BPH. Infected hoppers appeared green and died within a few days. With the spore concentration used, we observed a significantly high mortality of 64.8% ($t = 16.97$ at $p = 0.05$ and $df = 18$).

In a similar experiment, concentrations of 0 , 6.4×10^3 , 6.4×10^4 , 6.4×10^5 , 6.4×10^6 , and 6.4×10^7 fungal spores/ml were sprayed onto 18-d-old BPH on 30-d-old-rice plants raised in pots (20 plants/pot) with standing water. Percentage mortality recorded was adjusted for mortality in control treatments using Abbott's formula (see table). The highest mortality rate (76%) was observed on the seventh day after spraying when a spore concentration of 6.4×10^5 was used. Further increase or decrease in spore concentrations produced a lower mortality rate. It is possible that while lower rates of spore concentration do not provide enough coverage, higher concentrations show self-limiting antagonistic effects on infection. We propose that *Metarrhizium* sp. be used as an effective agent in integrated pest management programs in combating BPH problems in wetland rice culture.

Percentage mortality of *Nilaparvata lugens* treated with various concentrations of *Metarrhizium* sp. (AB301/1).^a

<i>Metarrhizium</i> spores/ml concentration	Days after treatment with spores						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6.4×10^7	0	0	0	3.3	6.6	20.0	33.3
6.4×10^6	0	0	16.6	26.6	30.0	50.0	56.6
6.4×10^5	0	6.6	10.0	26.6	33.3	53.3	76.6
6.4×10^4	0	6.6	10.0	10.0	13.3	16.6	20.0
6.4×10^3	0	3.3	3.3	3.3	6.6	6.6	10.0

^aMortality values are adjusted for control treatment values using Abbott's formula.

rior to inoculating fungus through a slit made on the body of the bag because it reduces contamination. ■

Flight activity of *Spodoptera fugiperda* (J. E. Smith) in acid savanna ricefields in northeastern Colombia

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Precise information on pest population dynamics is needed for implementing integrated pest management (IPM) programs. Since rice was introduced to the acid savanna soils in northeastern Colombia, farmers have complained that the fall armyworm (FAW) *Spodoptera fugiperda* (J. E. Smith) causes economic damage and reduced yields. Farmers often use up to two insecticide applications per season to control the pest without knowing the pest population dynamics and density.

A 3-yr study was conducted to determine flying patterns of *S. fugiperda* adults in commercial savanna rice-growing areas of Colombia. At each of three localities in the Cauca Department, two sticky traps with pheromone lures were placed within ricefields, 1 m above the ground. Lures were replaced every 45 d. Adults/trap were recorded twice a month. The mean number of adults/month was calculated for each locality (see table).

In general, the mean number of adults/month was low across three localities. The most collected was 34 males/trap during January at Santa Rosa and La Libertad, although rice is planted from April to early June. Eleven males/trap were counted at Matazul during July, but FAW population was below 5 males/trap during most of the year. This high number at Matazul coincides with the commercial rice-growing season, while the higher infestation rates at Santa Rosa and La Libertad occur when no rice was in the fields. This suggests that FAW population increases at Santa Rosa and La

Mean number of *S. fugiperda* ($\pm$ SEM) in pheromone traps in three localities in Colombia, 1990-92.

Month	Insects/trap (no.) ($\pm$ SEM)		
	Santa Rosa	La Libertad	Matazul
January	33.2 $\pm$ 3.7	28.2 $\pm$ 3.2	6.0 $\pm$ 1.6
February	1.3 $\pm$.3	1.9 $\pm$ 0.4	0.15 $\pm$ 0.1
March	4.6 $\pm$ 1.3	5.6 $\pm$ 1.6	0.81 $\pm$ 0.4
April	11.5 $\pm$ 1.9	8.0 $\pm$ 1.5	0.54 $\pm$ 0.2
May	16.4 $\pm$ 2.3	8.5 $\pm$ 1.3	3.5 $\pm$ 1.0
June	21.3 $\pm$ 2.7	21.8 $\pm$ 1.9	10.11 $\pm$ 1.4
July	23.6 $\pm$ 3.9	13.8 $\pm$ 2.4	11.6 $\pm$ 1.4
August	16.6 $\pm$ 2.9	10.7 $\pm$ 2.0	2.6 $\pm$ 0.6
September	15.2 $\pm$ 7.8	7.1 $\pm$ 1.5	1.5 $\pm$ 0.4
October	17.5 $\pm$ 3.1	21.1 $\pm$ 10.3	2.9 $\pm$ 1.3
November	21.8 $\pm$ 2.8	18.6 $\pm$ 2.9	2.9 $\pm$ 1.3
December	20.5 $\pm$ 2.7	16.6 $\pm$ 2.9	1.4 $\pm$ 0.4
Mean	15.6 $\pm$ 0.79	12.4 $\pm$ 1.00	3.8 $\pm$ 0.40

Libertad were related to weeds in the fields. Adult FAW activity at La Libertad and Santa Rosa was continuous during

the cropping season. However, at Matazul, adult flight activity was higher on 6- to 90-d-old plants.

No correlation was found between adult flight activity and larval damage on rice growing in acid soils. Population levels observed during the rice-growing season were low. Population levels observed in our study were low compared with FAW densities in other areas, suggesting that insecticide applications may not be necessary.

These findings will help farmers and IPM personnel make informed decisions about FAW control. Further research is needed to correlate adult flight activity with larval density and yield reduction, and to correlate FAW incidence with availability of alternate hosts. ■

Applying insecticides at early stage of rice cropping season may cause brown plant-hopper resurgence

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Five fields (about 0.1 ha each) in northern Zhejiang Province were selected to test the effects of early insecticide application on brown planthopper (BPH) population dynamics during the second irrigated rice cropping season. Japonica rice varieties were transplanted in late July to early August.

In general, macropters immigrate into ricefields after transplanting and produce two generations (called generations 4 and 5 in Zhejiang) during the season. Damage to plants peaks with generation 5, around late September.

Each field was divided into three equal plots. Plot A served as the control, where insecticide was sprayed; plot B received one insecticide application at the early stage (about 20 d after transplanting) to control stem borer; and plot C was the same as B with an additional insecticide (buprofezin) application at the late stage to control BPH if the farmer thought it necessary (see table).

Mobile stages of BPH, its eggs, and main predators (spiders, mirids) were surveyed by tapping plants to make the insects and spiders drop onto a 30- x 40-cm plate that was placed at the base of the plants.

Growth rates from generations 4 and 5 in the plots sprayed with insecticides

were significantly higher than those in the control plots of the same fields ($t = 3.74, p < 0.01$) (see table). The key period affecting BPH population growth from generation 4 to 5 after insecticide spraying is during generation 4 nymph peak to generation 5 egg peak. Inappropriate spraying, including both the type of

Comparison of BPH growth rates under different insecticide treatments. Zhejiang, China.

Plot no.	Treatment ^a		G5 ^b Egg/G4 ^c Peak		G5 Peak/G5 Egg		G5 Peak/G4 Peak	
	DAT	Insecticide	Growth rate ^d	Ratio to check	Growth rate $\times$ 100	Ratio to check	Growth rate ^d	Ratio to check
1A	Check ^e		16.35		18.96		3.11	
1B	27	M+D	27.14	1.66	23.33	1.23	6.33	2.04
1C	27	M+D	38.62	2.36	21.96	1.16	8.48	2.73
2A	Check		8.47		43.88		3.72	
2B	23	M+D	8.70	1.03	41.91	0.96	3.65	0.98
2C	23	M+D	11.61	1.37	45.83	1.04	5.32	1.43
3A	Check		27.20		14.16		3.85	
3B	21	M+D	32.64	1.20	19.54	1.38	6.38	1.66
3C	21	M+D	39.02	1.43	14.46	1.02	5.64	1.46
4A	Check		33.02		7.25		2.40	
4B	18	Tri	69.49	2.10	10.48	1.45	7.28	3.03
4C	22	SCS+Tric	62.94	1.91	13.93	1.92	8.76	3.65
5A	Check		26.72		36.65		9.79	
5B	21	Tri	31.53	1.18	46.92	1.28	14.79	1.51
5C	25	SCS+B	50.00	2.25	32.00	0.87	16.00	1.63
	Mean			1.65		1.23		2.01
	SE			0.15		0.10		0.27
	t			4.33 ^{**f}		2.18		3.74 ^{**}

^aDAT = d after transplanting; insecticides: M = methamidophos; D = deltamethrin; Tri = triazophos; SCS = shachongshua (cartap-like); Tric = trichlorphon; B = buprofezin. ^bG5 = generation 5; ^cG4 = generation 4; ^dGrowth rate = (BPH Count in stage (t+1)/(BPH count in stage t)); ^eCheck means no insecticide applied; ^f** = mean is significantly greater than 1 (t = test, p < 0.01).